

FPGA IMPLEMENTATION OF A SIMPLE LOSSLESS ALGORITHM (SLA) FOR ON-BOARD SATELLITE HYPERSPECTRAL DATA COMPRESSION

Vijay Joshi, Sheeba Rani J.*

Department of Avionics, Indian Institute of Space Science and Technology,
Thiruvananthapuram, India

8th International Workshop on On-Board Payload Data Compression OBPDC 2022

September 28-30, 2022

Outline

- Introduction
- Need of on-board compression
- Objectives
- FPGA Architecture for SLA
- Work in Progress & Future Works
- References

Need of on-board compression

- Resolution of remote sensors & data rates continue to increase, available down-link bandwidth is comparatively stable.
- Large data to be steadily transmitted to ground within limited time & using fixed computational resources on-board.

$$DataRate = \frac{1}{GSD^2} \circ SW \circ v|_{ground} (h) \circ DR$$

Need of on-board compression

Kristian Manthey, David Krutz, and Ben Juurlink. "A new real-time system for image compression on-board satellites". In: ESA/CNES On-Board Payload Data Compression (OBPDC), Venice, Italy (2014).

Objectives

- To develop an algorithm for on-board satellite hyperspectral image compression with:
 - i) Least computational complexity w.r.t. state-of-the-art on-board standards.
 - ii) Ability to handle high data acquisition rates and dynamic range of instruments.
 - iii) Comparable compression effectiveness w.r.t. state-of-the-art on-board standards.
 - iv) Efficient hardware implementation for real-time applications.

Objectives

- To develop an algorithm for on-board satellite hyperspectral image compression with:
 - i) Least computational complexity w.r.t. state-of-the-art on-board standards.
 - ii) Ability to handle high data acquisition rates and dynamic range of instruments.
 - iii) Comparable compression effectiveness w.r.t. state-of-the-art on-board standards.
 - iv) Efficient hardware implementation for real-time applications.
- To extend use of algorithm for on-board data processing applications like image classification, object detection.

Lossless Compression Overview (CCSDS 123.0-B-1)

Lossless Compression using proposed method

Lossless Compression using proposed method

- Directional local differences are used to utilize neighbourhood correlation of the pixel.
- Minimization is done using factors, which are calculated using previously processed neighbourhood pixels.

Minimization stage

Minimization stage

- Value of Minimization factors
- Selection of optimal minimization factor
Neighbour Driven Decision Making (NDDM)

Flow Chart

Challenges & Solutions applied

Challenges	Solution attempted
To select optimal value in local difference selection, factor selection and smoothing factor selection stage	Decision based on mode and previously processed pixel (NDDM).
To make a positive integer based algorithm	$M(a) = \begin{cases} 2a & a \geq 0 \\ 2 a - 1 & a < 0 \end{cases}$
To allow skipping further minimization when already residual in specified range	NDDM allows a user defined parameter to control stages of minimization.

Key features of SLA

Characteristics	Parameters incorporated
1. Computational complexity	Number of operations for processing a pixel
2. Compression effectiveness	bps
3. Flexibility	User controlled parameters
4. Error containment	Limiting impact of packet loss
5. Robustness	Ability to tackle instrument defects

- SLA uses causal neighbourhood with four spatial and one spectral neighbour and decision making too is done using immediate neighbours, thus possible error caused during memory access and possible communication packet loss is contained in the region.
- Robustness i.e. ability to handle instrument defects is inherent as previous pixels are used to take decision about best choice and even if decision is not correct, it will affect compression performance only.

FPGA Architecture of full four causal mode of SLA

Memory distribution

For accessing spatial neighbourhood of current pixel:
Shift register based SIPO design

For accessing spectral neighbourhood of current pixel:

BRAM IP of FPGA (SIPO design also used with BRAM IP when simultaneously more than two pixels are needed from spectral neighbourhood)

Customized SIPO for directional west mode of SLA

Timing diagram for Full directional west mode of algorithm

Estimated memory requirements for full modes of SLA

Mode of Algorithm	Estimated Memory Requirements
West	$N_x.N_y + N_x + 3 + 1$
North	$N_x.N_y + N_x + N_x + 3$
Spectral	$N_x.N_y + N_x.N_y + N_x + 3$
Four causal neighbourhood	$N_x.N_y + N_x.N_y + 2.(N_x + 3)$

Resource utilization

FPGA Resource (for BRAM IP)	Utilization	FPGA Resource (Remaining design)	Utilization
LUT	1296	LUT	4954
FF	66	FF	658
BRAM	480	BRAM	0
URAM	0	URAM	0
DSP	0	DSP	0

Resource	Utilization	Available	Utilization %
LUT	6250	1182240	0.53
LUTRAM	16	591840	0.00
FF	740	2364480	0.03
BRAM	480	2160	22.22
IO	58	832	6.97
BUFG	1	1800	0.06

Resource utilization for pre-processing stage of full west mode

Resource utilization

FPGA Resource (for BRAM IP)	Utilization	FPGA Resource (Remaining design)	Utilization
LUT	1296	LUT	4954
FF	66	FF	658
BRAM	480	BRAM	0
URAM	0	URAM	0
DSP	0	DSP	0

Resource	Utilization	Available	Utilization %
LUT	6250	1182240	0.53
LUTRAM	16	591840	0.00
FF	740	2364480	0.03
BRAM	480	2160	22.22
IO	58	832	6.97
BUFG	1	1800	0.06

Resource utilization hierarchy

Name	CLB LUTs (1182240)	CLB Registers (2364480)	CARRY8 (147780)	F7 Muxes (591120)	F8 Muxes (295560)	Block RAM Tile (2160)	Bonded IOB (832)	GLOBAL CLOCK BUFFERS (1800)
▼ N top	6250	740	338	372	160	480	58	1
└─ dut_spec_pr (dff_0)	139	16	18	0	0	0	0	0
└─ dut_spec (dff)	183	16	12	0	0	0	0	0
> └─ dut_smt_selector (smt_selector)	58	32	4	0	0	0	0	0
└─ dut_smt_min (smt_min)	0	16	0	0	0	0	0	0
> └─ dut_sipo (sipo)	1118	149	82	15	0	0	0	0
> └─ dut_pr_band (blk_mem_gen_0)	1296	66	0	320	160	480	0	0
> └─ dut_ls (ls)	440	30	9	0	0	0	0	0
> └─ dut_ld_selector (ld_selector)	991	51	67	32	0	0	0	0
> └─ dut_ld (ld)	310	64	8	0	0	0	0	0
> └─ dut_factor_minimization (factor_min)	27	32	2	0	0	0	0	0
> └─ dut_fac_sel (fac_selector)	1591	145	100	5	0	0	0	0

Aspects to improve

➤ Compression performance is comparable to on-board satellite hyperspectral image compression methods other than CCSDS 123.0-B-1 standards, which has best compression performance.

Aspects to improve

- Compression performance is comparable to on-board satellite hyperspectral image compression methods other than CCSDS 123.0-B-1 standards, which has best compression performance.

- SLA can perform better by incorporating inter-band and intra-band mode selection strategies.

Future Works

- BIP & BIL scanning order implementations for detecting cloud regions in the given image using spectral signatures. This will further enable on-board classification and detection.

Future Works

- Customized ASIC implementation of encoder of SLA in BSQ scanning order with high speed and low power optimizations.

- Customized ASIC implementation of encoder of SLA in BSQ scanning order with high speed and low power optimizations.
- Circuit level design of approximate comparators and memory architecture as per the algorithm requirements will be done.

- Customized ASIC implementation of encoder of SLA in BSQ scanning order with high speed and low power optimizations.
- Circuit level design of approximate comparators and memory architecture as per the algorithm requirements will be done.
- Decisions are made using previously processed pixels and in three modes of algorithm, there is possibility of in-memory-computations which will be explored.

References

- › Khalid Sayood, Introduction to Data Compression, Fourth Edition, Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc. San Francisco, CA, USA ©2012.
- › Kristian Manthey, David Krutz, and Ben Juurlink., “A new real-time system for image compression on-board satellites”. In: ESA/CNES On-Board Payload Data Compression (OBPDC), Venice, Italy (2014).
- › Nebout et al., “On-board Optical Image Compression for Future High Resolution Remote Sensing Systems”. In: SPIE Proceedings 4115 (2000), pp. 332–346.
- › Enrique et.al., “Review and implementation of the emerging CCSDS recommended standards for multi-spectral and hyper-spectral lossless image coding,” Data Comp., Comm. And Processing (CCP), 2011.
- › The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems, Lossless Multispectral and Hyperspectral Image Compression Recommended Standard CCSDS 123.0-B-1, 2012.
- › Santos et.al., “Multispectral and Hyperspectral Lossless Compressor for Space Applications (HyLoC): A Low-Complexity FPGA Implementation of the CCSDS 123 Standard,” IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing, VOL. 9, NO. 2, February 2016.
- › Tsigkanos et.al., “A 3.3 Gbps CCSDS 123.0-B-1 Multispectral & Hyperspectral Image Compression Hardware Accelerator on a Space-Grade SRAM FPGAs,” IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computing, 2018.
- › The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems, Low-Complexity Lossless and Near-Lossless Multispectral and hyperspectral Image Image Compression Recommended Standard CCSDS 123.0-B-2, 2019.

Target: On-board processing and object detection

Thank you.